

ERIC Forum Implementation Project

Annual Meeting Report

Work Package 6 - Deliverable 6.13

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Executive summary

The document reports the outcome of the ERIC Forum Annual meeting, which took place in Brussels on the 5th and 6th February 2020.

The event was divided in two distinct moments:

- the project's annual meeting;
- the ERIC Forum general assembly. The assembly was itself divided in 2 parts:
 - a set of open sessions, enriched by the participation of stakeholders as both speakers and attendees, during which the Forum discussed high level science policy issues;
 - a closed session, reserved to the ERIC Forum members, to discuss internal matters related to the Forum.

The report outlines the impact of the project in the life of the ERIC Forum and underlines how the projects supports the development of the Forum, while having large impact on the European research infrastructure policy.

Main outcomes:

- The event was opened by the Croatian ministry of research (representing the Croatian presidency of the EU) and the European Commission Director of DG RTD's Common Implementation Centre.
- The new governance model was approved by the Forum (deliverable 2.) and the new Executive Board, including new Chair and Vice Chair, entered in office.
- A report on the project's outcomes was presented to the Forum and approved by the project's partners.
- WP6 and WP3 contributed to the organization of event's sessions, that contributed to the development of the WPs' deliverables, maximizing the projects funds and impact.

Important notice: this report is structured to report on the two event moments separately, for clarity and comprehensiveness. Due to logistical and organizational reasons (speakers' availability, costs etc.) the 2 moments were intertwined within the whole event agenda. Therefore, the order of the items in this report does not follow strictly the order of sessions within the event's agenda.

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Document log

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Table of Contents

EXECUTIVE SUMMARY1

AGENDA6

ERIC FORUM GENERAL ASSEMBLY9

 Present 9

 Proxies..... 9

 Apologies..... 9

 Structure of the ERIC Forum General Assembly 9

 Agenda of the open session..... 10

 Agenda of the closed session..... 10

 Open sessions 10

 Opening..... 10

 Solutions for a Sustainable EOSC..... 11

 Research Infrastructures and the Missions 11

 ERIC Forum Dinner 12

 Closed sessions 13

 Results of the elections..... 13

 New Rules of Procedure 14

 Introduction of the new ERIC Forum Executive Board and discussion on 2020 priorities..... 14

 Chair’s summary of main discussion points..... 18

ERIC FORUM IMPLEMENTATION PROJECT ANNUAL MEETING, TUESDAY, 6TH FEBRUARY 2020.....20

 Present 20

 Agenda 20

 Amendments to the grant agreement..... 20

 Financials and reporting 20

 Plan for 2020..... 21

 Report from WPs 21

 WP1..... 21

 WP2..... 21

 WP3..... 21

WP4.....	21
WP5.....	22
WP6.....	22
Approval of the reporting.....	23
ANNEXES	24
Annex 1: Participants’ list	24
Annex 2: Robert Jones’ presentation.....	24
Annex 3: Package of presentations from the Horizon Europe sessions.....	24
Annex 4: Package of presentation from ERIC Forum Dinner.....	24
Annex 5: Florindi’s presentation: “ERIC Forum Elections 2020 - Process & outcomes”	24
Annex 6: ERIC Forum election process	24
Annex 7: Election committee voting report	24
Annex 8: Oepen’s presentation: ““Journey” to a permanent Governance model”	24
Annex 9: Rules of Procedure for the implementation of the “MoU for the establishment of the ERIC Forum”	24
Annex 10: Womersley’s presentation: “Setting the agenda for 2020”	24
Annex 11: Participants’ list and signing sheet for the ERIC Forum Implementation Project Annual Meeting	24
Annex 12: Presentation for the ERIC Forum Implementation Project Annual Meeting	24
Annex 13: Ussi-Fauvel’s presentation: “WP3 Operations, HR, Finance, Administratiion”	24

DAY 1. WEDNESDAY, FEBRUARY 5TH

TIME	PROGRAM DESCRIPTION
12:00 – 13:00	Lunch
SESSION 1 (closed session)	
13:00 – 14:00	<p>ERIC Forum new governance – Presentation and decision</p> <p><i>ERIC Forum Chair: Ron Dekker</i></p> <p>With the new governance coming up, it is time to familiarise ourselves with the new rules governing the Forum, and meet the new Chair, Executive Committee and Secretariat.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Before this, the ERIC Forum General Assembly must vote on the outcome of the election of Chair and Vice Chair and on the proposed members by the clusters of the Executive Board. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Election process and evaluation of the governance – <i>Francesco Florindi, Chair of the Election Committee</i> (10 min). Introduction of the new Chair and Executive Committee (40 min) ▪ How did we get there? Reports on governance from WP2 <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Journey to the new rules – <i>Andrea Oepen, WP2 Leader</i> (10 min)
SESSION 2 (closed session)	
14:00 – 15:00	<p>Research Policy Brief – Presentation – Discussion – Conclusion</p> <p><i>Jacques Demotes, Ute Gunsenheimer: WP6 Strategy</i></p> <p>ERIC Forum Policy Brief: Funding models for access to ERIC multinational / transnational services.</p>
15:00 – 15:30	Coffee break – start of the open sessions

SESSION 3

15:30 – 16:00	<p>Opening of the open sessions</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • <i>Tome Antičić, State Secretary, Ministry of Science and Education, Republic of Croatia</i> • <i>Updates from the European Commission</i> <p>Followed by Q&A with participants.</p>
SESSION 4	
16:00 – 16:45	<p>Solutions for a Sustainable EOSC – Presentations and Discussions</p> <p><i>Bob Jones, CERN and Member of the EOSC Sustainability Working Group</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Presentation based on the ‘Tinman’ report and opportunity to provide feedback by ERIC Forum
SESSION 5	
16:45 – 17:45	<p>Research Infrastructures and the Missions – Presentation – Discussion</p> <p><i>Chair: Ron Dekker</i></p> <p>Introductions on the five Missions (25 min.)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ 1: Adapting to Climate Change, incl. Societal Transformation ▪ 2: Cancer ▪ 3: Soil health and food ▪ 4: Climate-neutral and smart cities ▪ 5: Healthy ocean, seas, coastal and inland waters <p>Follow up on Missions by the ERICs – discussion and working towards a joint statement (20 min.)</p>
17:45 – 19:00	<p>Free time/ Guided tour</p> <p>Option to have a Guided Tour to the Parliamentarium or European House of History.</p>
19:00 – 21:30	<p>ERIC Forum Dinner</p> <p>Renaissance Hotel, Rue de Parnasse 19, 1050 Brussels</p> <p>19.00 Welcome and Drinks</p> <p>19.30 Dinner</p>

DAY 2. THURSDAY, FEBRUARY 6TH

SESSION 6 (closed session)	
09:00 – 10:00	<p>Setting the Agenda of the ERIC Forum – Discussion</p> <p>The new Executive Board takes the floor to listen to the needs and perspectives of the ERICs and present their vision for their mandate.</p>
SESSION 7 (closed session)	
10:00 – 11:00	<p>Operations, Administration, HR and Finance of ERICs – Results of the survey</p> <p><i>Chairs: Anne-Charlotte Fauvel, Anton Ussi - WP 3 Operations, Administration, HR and Finance of ERICs.</i></p>
11:00 – 11:30	Coffee break
SESSION 8 (closed session)	
11:30 – 12:30	<p>ERIC Forum Project</p> <p><i>Chair: Francesco Florindi, Project Coordinator</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Finalisation of the 1st project amendment ▪ Financial management of the project ▪ WPs reports ▪ Plan for 2020
12:30 – 14:00	Lunch and departure

ERIC Forum General Assembly

Date and place: 5th and 6th February 2020 – Renaissance Hotel, Brussels, Belgium

Present

The full list of participants is available as Annex 1.

Below the list of ERIC Forum voting members:

- Ron Dekker, CESSDA-ERIC;
- Franciska de Jong, CLARIN;
- Anton Ussi, EATRIS;
- Sverre Quale, ECCSEL;
- Jacques Demotes, ECRIN;
- John Womersley, ESS (spallation);
- Wolfgang Fecke, EU-OPENSSCREEN;
- John Eriksson, EuroBioImaging;
- Francisco Colomer, JIVE;
- Christos Arvanitidis, LifeWatch.

Proxies

The Chairs recognise the following proxies:

- Francesco Florindi can vote on behalf of BBMRI;
- Carlo Rizzuto can vote on behalf of CERIC and EPOS;
- Arnaud Roi can vote on behalf of DARIAH;
- Alexandra Vasic can vote on behalf of EMBRC;
- Paola Materia can vote on behalf of EMSO;
- Lorna Ryan, can vote on behalf of ESS (social);
- Andrea Oepen can vote on behalf of SHARE.

Written copies for each proxy are archived on the ERIC Forum SharePoint.

Apologies

- ICOS
- INSTRUCT
- Euro-ARGO

The Chair recognised 18 voting members.

The quorum is set at 12 votes.

Structure of the ERIC Forum General Assembly

The ERIC Forum General Assembly was divided in 2 parts:

- a set of open sessions, enriched by the participation of stakeholders as both speakers and attendees, during which the Forum discussed high level science policy issues;
- a closed session, reserved to the ERIC Forum members, to discuss internal matters related to the Forum.

Agenda of the open session

- Opening
- Solutions for a Sustainable EOSC
- Research Infrastructures and the Missions
- ERIC Forum Dinner

Agenda of the closed session

- Results of the elections
- New Rules of Procedure
- Introduction of the new ERIC Forum Executive Board and discussion on 2020 priorities

Open sessions

Opening

The ERIC Forum general assembly open sessions brought together more than 23 different ERIC and ERIC-to-be, as well as representatives from the European Commission (DG RTD), Ministries of Science, the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI), Research councils and more.

The open sessions focused on various aspects, spanning the new governance model of the ERIC Forum, ERICs' funding models and access to RIs, European Open Science Cloud's sustainability, Horizon Europe missions and more. It was also an opportunity to discuss with the ERIC Forum's stakeholders about the added value expected from the Forum.

The participation of external participants brought an additional value to the discussions considering their wide knowledge and different perspectives of the RIs and ERICs' landscapes.

Figure 1: the newly elected ERIC Forum Executive Board with Ms Anna Panagopoulou, Director, Common Implementation Centre at European Commission's DG RTD (3rd from left) and Tome Antičić, State Secretary at the Ministry of Science and Education of Croatia (4th from left).

Tome Antičić, State Secretary at the Ministry of Science and Education of Croatia, opened the event and defined the added value expected from the ERIC Forum as follow: *“The EU has a very large and very diverse*

number of research infrastructures. It is in fact quite difficult to coordinate them, to see where there could be synergies among them, to find mechanisms of funding them – including maintenance costs. The ERIC Forum could very much facilitate these issues, and hopefully it will have a more explicit role regarding that in the future.”

Looking at the Croatian research environment, Mr. Antičić said: *“ERICs are a fantastic mechanism for the best Croatian researchers to work with the best facilities and with the best EU researchers. The transnational access has in fact significantly improved the quality of Croatian research, and the Croatian TNA facilities have greatly benefited from the influx and project money of top researchers from all around the world. Further, and larger, support for ERICs is definitely a priority for Croatia.”*

Mr Antičić’s presentation was followed by a contribution from Ms Anna Panagopoulo, Director of the Common Implementation Centre at the European Commission’s DG RTD. Ms Panagopoulo delivered a speech on the role of research infrastructures in the upcoming Horizon Europe Framework Programme, and the work the European Commission is doing to update the ERIC guidelines.

Solutions for a Sustainable EOSC

Ron Dekker chaired the open session to the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC) and the future developments of the EOSC relevant to the research infrastructures.

Robert Jones (CERN) Rapporteur of the EOSC Sustainability Working Group delivered a presentation on the key past achievements of the EOSC, and the results of the EOSC Sustainability Working Group to provide strategic, legal and financing recommendations for an operational, scalable and sustainable EOSC federation after 2020 (annex 2)

Research Infrastructures and the Missions

In the context of the ERIC Forum Annual Meeting, a session on the role of RIs in the Horizon Europe Missions was organised.

Ron Dekker chaired the session.

Five ERICs volunteered to provide more information on each Mission, and to suggest a possible way forward (see annex 3):

1. Adapting to Climate Change – Ron Dekker, CESSDA
2. Cancer – Francesco Florindi, BBMRI & Anton Ussi, EATRIS
3. Soil Health and Food – Sven Fahrner, EMPHASIS
4. Climate-Neutral and Smart Cities – Ornela De Giacomo, CERIC
5. Oceans – Christos Arvanitidis, LIFEWATCH

A discussion on the role of the ERICs in the Missions ensued.

The Assembly agreed the following:

- **The ERIC Forum shall produce a short position paper on the role of the ERICs in the Horizon Europe Missions in Q1-2 2020**, focused on the quality services provided by the ERICs, the long term

sustainability of the Missions objectives and the overall role of ERICs in the research panorama in Europe;

- **The ERIC Forum shall support the production of Mission-specific position paper, led by the volunteers who presented at the meeting, by Q1-2 2020.** These position paper will be produced and endorsed only by the ERIC contributing to the specific Mission. The scope, main messages of each paper shall be specific to each cluster/mission. **The ERIC Forum (Secretariat) will help to provide similar layouts and general structures** but will not influence the content.

ERIC Forum Dinner

A working dinner was organized on the evening of February 5th, at the Renaissance Hotel in Brussels. Attendees included ERIC representatives, ERIC Committee Representatives, ESFRI representatives, and European Commission representatives.

The dinner provided the opportunity to make a preliminary presentation of the policy report (WP6, linked to deliverable 6.7) to representatives of the ERIC Committee and the RI Committee. Prior to the dinner, all attendants received a concept sheet that briefly introduced the work of this WP (annex 4), and the ongoing preparation of the policy report. During the dinner, JIVE, LIFEWATCH, INSTRUCT and ECRIN, shared their current models for funding access to their services through a series of presentations (annex 4). Their presentations showcased the diversity of the funding models that ERICs have put in place for their users to access their services.

The presentations were followed by a general discussion, where ERICs and committee members shared their insight on the diversity of the ERICs' funding models, the importance of their sustainability, and the importance of increasing their visibility and showcasing their success stories and the breadth of their impact in the European research ecosystem.

The feedback obtained during the dinner, and during the discussions at the ERIC Forum meeting, will be integrated into a second draft of the policy report (deliverable 6.7). This second draft will be presented and discussed in the first ERIC Forum seminar, that will take place in the third quarter of 2020. Representatives from all relevant funding bodies will be invited to attend. Recommendations on the evolution of funding mechanisms for access to ERICs and for the sustainability of ERICs will be co-constructed with the attending stakeholders and the policy report will be finalized.

Closed sessions

Results of the elections

Florindi presents the election process and its results (annex 5).

The election was overseen by an Election Committee selected by the ERIC Directors on 16.10.2019 and composed of:

- Ivana Ilijasic Versic, CESSDA
- Volker Röhling, ECCSEL
- Francesco Florindi, BBMRI

The Election Committee produced an election procedure in collaboration with the Charis (annex 6), a report following the reception of the candidatures, and a final report on the results of the elections (annex 7). All documents have been shared with the ERIC Directors on the 30th January 2020.

Following a request from CERIC, the Assembly is asked to formally approve the election procedure used by the Election Committee:

- In favour: 16
- Against: 2
- Abstained: 0

The Assembly approves the election procedure.

The Election Committee reports that the submission of candidatures and voting processes were carried out in line with the new Rules of Procedure.

Furthermore, the Chairs and Election Committee received the following nominations for the remaining three positions within the Executive Board of the ERIC Forum:

- Franciska de Jong, CLARIN,
- Wolfgang Fecke, EU-OPENSREEN
- Juan Miguel González Aranda, LifeWatch

In line with the election procedure, the Chairs call the Assembly to approve the results of the elections, including the nomination of the members of the Executive Board:

- In favour: 18
- Against: 0
- Abstained: 0

The Assembly approves the results of the elections.

The new Executive Board is composed as following:

- Chair: John Womersley, ESS (spallation)
- Vice Chair: Anton Ussi, EATRIS
- Other members: Franciska de Jong, CLARIN, Wolfgang Fecke, EU-OPENSREEN, Juan Miguel González Aranda, LifeWatch.

New Rules of Procedure

Andrea Oepen presents the Rules of Procedures approved by the ERICs directors (annex 8). Oepen explains the process that led to the finalisation of the rules, and stresses the advantages of the new governance structure, that will allow for more transparency and effectiveness in decision making.

Oepen highlights that the ERIC Directors approved the general approach to the rules during the Directors' meeting in Amsterdam (October 2019), and mandated WP2 to finalise the rules in line with the discussion held in Amsterdam. Consequently, WP2 submitted the final version of the rules for approval on the 16th January 2020.

Oepen reports that further, minor comments were shared by few Directors since the expiry of the deadline. Those comments do not change the meaning of the rules, and have been included in the final version of the rules, that is made available to the Directors for signing (annex 9).

Oepen stresses that 2020 will serve as a test year for the rules: WP2 will continue to work on improving the rules based on the practical implementation. All ERICs are invited to submit their comments and edits to the rules throughout 2020.

Introduction of the new ERIC Forum Executive Board and discussion on 2020 priorities

The newly elected Executive Committee presents its vision for 2020 and opens a conversation with all ERICs to define the priority areas for action in 2020.

John Womersley delivers a presentation on the vision of the Executive Board (annex 10). Womersley stresses on the need for the Executive Board to be truly representative of the needs and opinions of the ERICs, and to be able to listen to their issues.

Following the presentation, the Board moderates a discussion among the participants, aiming at collecting feedback on the vision of the Board and key issues faced by each ERIC.

- Ron Dekker, CESSDA:
 - ERICs should be eligible to apply for funding at national level. Currently that is not the case in Norway, for example.
 - National funding schemes should take into consideration the legal structure of ERICs when designing funding schemes. Example: Norway's bonus system: the government provides 25% bonus funding to consortia winning EU funding. However, ERICs national nodes appear on the grant agreements as TLPs, therefore are not visible on the grant agreement, hence they do not receive the bonus. As a result, NN have an incentive to participate to EU calls autonomously.
- Lorna Ryan ESS (social): the implementation of GDPR is not sufficiently addressed by the ERICs. ESS established few best practices at operational level, not just at scientific level, that can benefit other ERICs.
- Francisco Colomer, JIVE: What is that the Forum can do that we cannot do as single ERICs?
 - Lobby countries for funding. ERIC Forum should focus on joint policy/advocacy.

- Membership expansion: JIVE has 6 only members, while other ERICs have over 20. ERIC Forum can help to share contacts at national level for all ERICs to find the right interlocutor at national level;
- Visibility: ERIC Forum should have a stronger communication strategy that can help all ERICs.
- Cristina Huertas, LifeWatch: what are the advantages for a country to join an ERIC? ERIC Forum could produce a matrix for “sell” the ERIC to new member states.
- Jacques Demotes, ECRIN supports Colomer’s point and adds that the Forum could create a Marketplace for member states to learn more about the ERICs and choose which ones to join.
- Carlo Rizzuto, CERIC: suggests the Forum to analyse the existing ERIC guidelines and prepare for an update of the document by the Commission. The Forum should start collecting ideas on how the guidelines could be amended/ should be written next time.
 - State budget: member states don’t usually foresee budget for ERICs in their annual financial planning. For international organisations, budgets are defined by parliamentary approval. The Forum could help to ensure member states include budgets for ERICs.
 - Staff: countries could agree that ERICs’ staff should be treated more or less the same way across the EU, not using EU instruments, but via intergovernmental agreement.
- Christos Arvanitidis, LifeWatch:
 - Brexit cannot stop us from working with UK researchers. Forum should come up with plan B to involve them.
 - Invest together in same areas – the Forum should increase the scientific connections among ERICs
 - The Forum could increase connections with the ERC and increase visibility by ERC/MSCG grantees.
- Eija Juurola, ACTRIS:
 - Sustainability is crucial factor for distributed infrastructures. Most of the investments happen at national level with national funding. The Forum could help identifying national funding sources.
 - The Forum could help to build partnerships with non-EU countries and expand membership.
- John Eriksson, EuroBioImaging:
 - Transnational access does not work anymore for ERICs– new models are needed at national/EU level
 - The Forum should play a bigger role in lobbying for funding from Horizon Europe. HE budget will be decided in February, but there will be important cuts through the negotiation.
- Andrea Oepen, SHARE
 - Time to have national budget lines the ERICs. SHARE has to deal with over 69 different funding sources and therefore financial planning is insecure at best.
 - Forum should be the interface with other RIs, in particular the EIROForum
- Kathrin Axt, SHARE:
 - The Forum should invite the EC at an event not to show what we are/have, but what we exist FOR – get the scientist to explain what is it that we do, in a simple language for policymakers. Instead of discussing about VAT, we should promote our role in science.
- Paola Materia, EMSO:

- On sustainability – EMSO is undergoing a global revision of its policies, including new calculations of membership fees. The Forum could help to harmonise this internal evaluation across ERICs, with ESFRI & MS
- Membership: expansion is important, but so is retention. It's difficult to define the intangible impact of ERICs.
- Francesco Florindi, BBMRI
 - The Forum should help to find a third membership model to the ERICs that would allow to expand collaborations beyond the EU without forcing third countries to adopt the ERIC regulation. This model should strike a balance between membership fee, limited access rights and open collaboration.
 - The prep-phases can benefit the most from the technical work of the Forum. They should be better involved in the life of the Forum.
- Sverre Quale, ECCSEL
 - The Forum should produce a list of common ministerial representatives, to help ERICs find the right person to speak to increase membership.
- Franciska de Jong, CLARIN
 - International collaboration should be a key focus of the Forum.
- Marleen Bosschaerts, MIRRI
 - The Forum can guide newcomers, beyond the ERIC guidelines.
- Anton Ussi, EATRIS:
 - Forum should become “super cool” – we need to create that nice atmosphere to kill the apathy from national ministries and national nodes.
- Carlo Rizzuto, CERIC:
 - ERC has become super cool. We're the second leg of basic science in Europe. We look after institutional entities, like ERC does for individual. Quality is paramount.
 - In Horizon Europe, RI funding will be delegated and managed by a new agency (not ERCEA). The Forum should insist that management of funding is done with same quality criteria of ERC.
- Lorna Ryan, ESS
 - ESS has MoU with Australia and South Africa that can serve as a model for other ERIC and perhaps the Forum.
- Juan Miguel González-Aranda, LIFEWATCH:
 - Importance of International Cooperation among RIs aspects. As an outstanding example, last EU-Latin America & Caribbean (EU-LAC) High Level Research Infrastructure meetings held in Andalusia (Spain) and San José (Costa Rica) on June & November 2019 respectively. LIFEWATCH was ranked of 1st interest by EU-LAC SOM (Senior Officers Meeting) on S&T.
- John Womersley:
 - Brain circulation: many ERICs have national nodes in low-medium income regions, suffering more from brain drain. EU/single market current set up does not help. ERICs can offer something at regional level that strengthens the nodes and retains talent.
 - Horizon Europe Missions – the Forum should advocate to keep them closer to the SDGs
 - Brexit in Horizon Europe – while UK authorities are confident they will be associated to Horizon Europe, we cannot take it for granted.

- ERICs experience with EIB loan:
 - ESS took a loan from EIB;
 - ELI too, in Hungary;
 - Fermi too, to cover the co-contribution of structural funds.

TNA → new thing

Brain circulation

missions → SDGs

UK in HEU ?

- . sustainable
- . visible
- . Super-cool

ERIC Forum Implementation Project Annual Meeting, Tuesday, 6th February 2020

Present

See participants list & signing sheet in annex 11.

Agenda

- Amendments to the grant agreement
- Financials & reporting
- Plan for 2020
- Reports from each WP
- Approval of the reporting
- AOB

In **bold**, you can find action points for the project partners and formal decisions by the Assembly.

Amendments to the grant agreement

Francesco Florindi reports the draft amendment has been submitted to the EC informally, and was well received (see annex 12). More justifications are needed, but the amendment should be approved soon. The amendment fixes several minor issues with the encoding of the project into the EC system, few partners changes and minor shifts to the budget.

Florindi suggests adding one more item to the amendment: the deletion of the Project's External Advisory Board. As it was not included in the final governance, the existence of the EAB for the project only does not justify the involvement of external parties.

The Project Assembly discussed and approves unanimously to delete the EAB.

Florindi also informs that the Executive Board of the Forum suggested the Project to include all prep-phases as new beneficiaries to the project, to showcase good will and support them financially for the participation to the Forum meetings.

The Project Assembly discussed and approves unanimously. A second amendment will be produced in 2020 to include all prep-phases as beneficiaries to the project. The Project Coordinator can discuss with the Commission alternative solutions should the amendment route be too complex or time consuming.

Financials and reporting

Florindi reports that all partners have contributed to the 1st voluntary financial reporting period, and all contributions were correct.

The second voluntary financial reporting will start shortly. BBMRI will contact each partner.

The first official financial reporting will take place in summer 2020.

Within February, the Project Coordinator will also produce the first annual report, with contributions from each WP.

Plan for 2020

Florindi reports that 2020 will see an increase in the activities of the Project. Several workshops and WP meetings will be organised, in particular by WP3 and WP6.

To facilitate the participation of all ERICs to the meetings, and to coordinate the organisation, **the Project Coordinator will liaise with the Executive Board to create a schedule of ERIC Forum/Project meetings for 2020, that will be shared soon.**

Report from WPs

WP1

The first three points on the agenda provide an overview of the activities of WP1.

WP2

Andrea Oepens' presentation (annex 8) provides an overview of the activities in WP2

WP3

Anne-Charlotte Fauvel and Anton Ussi present the results of the WP3 survey and the plan for WP3 for 2020 (annex 13).

WP3 produced four surveys prepared with task leaders and WP contributors open for responses between November 2019 and January 2020, covering the following topics. The results of each survey were produced and presented by different task leaders:

- Budgeting and financial reporting – Aleandro Furlani, EMSO
- Procurement, VAT, customs – Grigor Obolenski, Euro-ARGO (absent, substituted by Fauvel)
- Employment, secondment, recruitment – EATRIS, EU-OPENSREEN
- Insurance, contracting, intellectual property - Lorna Ryan, ESS (social)

Next steps for 2020:

- Face-to-face/remote interviews (Spring)
- Two face-to-face workshops for exchange of best practices

WP4

Ute Gusenheimer reports (annex 12) on the 2019 activities. The WP achieved three main objectives:

- It opened a dialogue with ESFRI to provide input on the ESFRI Monitoring Report
- It produced a Joint position paper on KPIs for the ERIC Forum
- It established a collaboration with the RI-PATHS project, therefore minimizing the risk of duplication of deliverables between the two projects.

Jana Kolar provides more details on the ESFRI monitoring report. The report outlines three possible implementation models

- Voluntary
- Semi-voluntary
- Compulsory, with ESFRI monitoring the results

Gusenheimer asks the partners if another reply to the ESFRI monitoring report is necessary. Kolar agrees to share the current draft of the 3 implementation routes discussed within ESFRI. **The Assembly discussed and agrees to explore a new position paper in reply to the latest ESFRI monitoring report.**

WP5

Salma Baghdadi reports on the achievements of WP5 and the metrics related to the ERIC Forum communications (annex 12).

The focus areas for 2020 will be:

- Reinforce the ERIC Forum branding: the public audience needs to be more aware of the ongoing activities of each WP.
- Strengthening the collaboration with RI-VIS with regard to the RIs' Communication toolkit.
- ERIC Forum toolkit: set up the technical framework in preparation of the publication.

Discussion:

- **To foster the promotion, Baghdadi recommends the ERICs to share with WP5 their organizations' activities, and inform in advance whenever presenting the ERIC Forum at an external event in order to timely communicate about it;**
- **Florindi suggests to organise a meeting WP5-Executive Board to edit the Forum communication strategy following the results of the discussion of this meeting;**
- **Several partners recommend WP5 to explore the production of a short video and/or a brochure on the Forum;**
- **Christos Arvanitidis recommends WP5 to set up an automatic repost of each ERICs news on the Forum website;**
- **Andrea Oepen suggests to produce a common brochure template for the Forum, including a description from each ERIC;**
- **John Womersley asks each ERIC to submit to WP5 information material that can be used by the Executive Board to provide more info on each ERICs operations/role and for quick reference;**
- **Federica Paina informs that the CORBEL project is preparing a brochure on success stories in life science RIs.**
- **Franciska de Jong shares that the Forum contact list is still not complete. She suggests WP5 to send again the contact list to all ERICs for another round of edits.**

WP6

Jacques Demotes presents the results of WP6 and plan for 2020 (annex 12).

The topic selected for 2020 is funding mechanisms for ERIC-supported projects.

The first draft of the policy brief was prepared in October/ November 2019 and will be updated following the discussion held in Brussels on the 5th February (ERIC Forum Dinner) and following the next ERIC Forum seminar (Q2-3 2020). The final policy brief will be published in Q3 2020.

Demotes requests feedback to all ERICs to identify who to invite at the next seminar.

[Approval of the reporting](#)

The ERIC Forum Implementation Project unanimously approves the reporting provided by the Project Coordinator and WP leaders, and the plan for 2020.

Annexes

Annex 1: Participants' list

Annex 2: Robert Jones' presentation

Annex 3: Package of presentations from the Horizon Europe sessions

Annex 4: Package of presentation from ERIC Forum Dinner

Annex 5: Florindi's presentation: "ERIC Forum Elections 2020 - Process & outcomes"

Annex 6: ERIC Forum election process

Annex 7: Election committee voting report

Annex 8: Oepen's presentation: "'Journey' to a permanent Governance model"

Annex 9: Rules of Procedure for the implementation of the "MoU for the establishment of the ERIC Forum"

Annex 10: Womersley's presentation: "Setting the agenda for 2020"

Annex 11: Participants' list and signing sheet for the ERIC Forum Implementation Project Annual Meeting

Annex 12: Presentation for the ERIC Forum Implementation Project Annual Meeting

Annex 13: Ussi-Fauvel's presentation: "WP3 Operations, HR, Finance, Administration"